

STUDY OF TRAFFIC VOLUME AND ITS SAFETY MEASUREMENTS AT VHANGA JUNCTION

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Abstract

A Traffic management system is needed to assure safe and effectual movement of people, goods and transportation. Safe and effectual movement of people, goods and transportation depend on the effectiveness of the traffic management system. Without effective planning and traffic management of the city, the existing road infrastructure cannot meet the future traffic demands of the city. Understanding the traffic volume is one of the most important elements of the traffic management system. This study was conducted to determine traffic flow characteristics and safety measurement through primary traffic flow surveys as well as skilled observations at Vhanga highway junction in Faridpur. Determination of the traffic volume was counted by manual counting method and the level of service was measured by Peak Hour Factor (PHF) method is the range of 0.86-0.90 that is D category. Moreover, calculation of Passenger Car Units (PCU's) for different types of vehicle had been made. An attempt has been completed to know the traffic patterns of the different time periods are indicated that Auto Rickshaw is most common vehicle. Throughout observation, this work has been found the average lane width and the average widths of shoulder are 9.5 feet (two lane) and 2.5 feet respectively. Due to insufficient lane and shoulder widths as well as no existence of signaling are caused negative impact such as congestions, accidents as well. Some of the remedial measures to increase the traffic safety by providing adequate lane number (4 or 6) and width, proper signaling and restricted scattered parking can be recommended based on the outcomes of the work.

Keywords: Traffic volume, PHF, PCU, Level of service

1. Introduction

Transportation is carrying civilization to a brighter future. In the recent years, transportation is one of the most burning problems in every territory of the globe. Every country is approaching as per their desires and try to resolve transportation issues as per the capabilities and resources they owe. While designing any structure it is necessary to calculate the loads coming on it to determine the reinforcement to be provided for safe functioning of the structure. In transportation volume serves the identical purpose. For planning, designing, scheduling, safe operation and development of transportation system the prime requisite is traffic volume [1].

Traffic Volume is simply the number of vehicles passing a section of a roadway. Expressing traffic volume as number of vehicles passing a given section of road or traffic lane per unit time will be inappropriate when several types of vehicles with widely varying static and dynamic characteristics are comprised in the traffic. The problem of measuring volume of such heterogeneous traffic has been addressed by converting the different types of vehicles into equivalent passenger cars and expressing the volume in terms of Passenger Car Unit (PCU) per hour. The interaction between moving vehicles under such heterogeneous traffic condition is highly complex. Again, volume is not constant. It increases with time. So, a continuous method of calculating volume is a matter of great importance for smooth functioning of transportation system. If volume data is not found on a continuous basis then the transportation system may fail and the economy of the country may face a great difficulty[2].

Road traffic safety means safe traffic operations which involves measures and methods to prevent road users from being injured or killed. As per media statistics, In Bangladesh more than 21 people lost their lives on roads each day. The main reasons for on-road casualties are bad road conditions, illiterate and unskilled drivers, faulty vehicles, poor traffic management, callousness of pedestrians, lack of political will, and poor enforcement. So, it is necessary to determine the various factors causing inconvenience to the road traffic such as congestion, travel time delays etc[3].

The main goal of this study is to determine the traffic volume and Level of Service (LOS) by using Peak Hour Factor (PHF) method at the Faridpur-Vhanga Highway junction point.

2. Methodology

To meet the objectives of the study traffic survey was conducted by manual counting method and the LOS is estimated by Peak Hour Factor (PHF) method. There are two effective methods of counting vehicle for volume

survey. They are (a) Manual Counting Method; (b) Automatic counting method. In this study we used the Manual Counting Method instead of Automatic Counting Method due to lack of instruments which are required for automatic counting. Manual Counting Method is divided into categories are (i) Direct method, and (ii) Indirect method

2.1 Direct Method

By this method data is counted by using hand tally and manual counter. We can obtain the traffic volume as well as vehicle classification. We have used this method during off peak hours. Road way geometry has been taken directly with hand tools.

2.2 Indirect Method

In this method the traffic volume data is collected by the video camera. Video is captured & after that data is collected by rewinding. At morning and evening time, we have used this method because of high traffic flow.

2.3 Peak Hour Factor Method

Traffic engineers focus on the peak-hour traffic volume in evaluating capacity and other parameters because it represents the most critical time. The analysis of level of service is based on peak rates of flow occurring within the peak hour because substantial short-term fluctuations typically occur during an hour. Common practice is to use a peak 15-minute rate of flow. Flow rates are usually expressed in vehicles per hour, not vehicles per 15 minutes.

Table 1: LOS with respect to its PHF

Peak Hour Factor Value	Level of Service (LOS)
0.7 or less	A
0.8 or less	B
0.85 or less	C
0.90 or less	D
0.95 or less	E
>1 or less	F

The relationship between the peak 15-minute flow rate and the full hourly volume is given by the Peak Hour Factor (PHF) as shown in the following equation (Authority, 2003). Peak Hour Factors in urban areas generally range between 0.80 and 0.98. Peak-Hour Factors over 0.95 are often indicative of high traffic volumes [4]. PHF was evaluated by the equation, Peak Hour Factor, $PHF = \frac{\text{Hourly Volume}}{4 * \text{Volume count at highest 15 minutes}}$ [5].

2.4 Passenger Car Units

Passenger Car Unit (PCU) is a metric used in Transportation Engineering, to assess traffic-flow rate on a highway. The PCU values given in the geometric design of Highways are given in Table 2 cited from [6]

Table 2: PCU values of different types of vehicles (MoC, 2010)

Categories	PCU
Passenger Car	1.00
Light Good Vehicle	1.00
Bus	3.00
Truck	3.00
Auto Rickshaw/ Motorcycle	0.75
Rickshaw/ Van	2.00
Bicycle	0.5

2.5 Description of study location

The location of the spot for traffic volume survey was started from Faridpur city old bus station to Vhanga junction point. Faridpur old bus station is very crowded area where buses are arrived and departed from the station. Vehicles from Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction and from Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station were counted. The different types of vehicles presents in this study area are Buses, Microbuses, Trucks, Cars, Auto Bikes, Motorcycles, and Bicycles etc

Fig. 1: Faridpur Old Bus Station to Vhanga Highway Junction Point (Google Map, 2020).

2.4 Date collection

The data collection for traffic volume study was conducted on 06 March 2019. It was Tuesday and it was a weekday. Time of data collection 01 (one hour) was divided into four time interval for volume study. That day was Sunny and clear day with the dry pavement condition. The observation for counting was conducted according to classification of vehicles with help of Stop watch, Tally sheet, Clip board and Video camera was used to record which is attached to a tripod stand. Number of enumerators on observation in this research was four.

2.5 Data Analysis

Both manual and video camera method (photographic) were used for the calculation of traffic volume of that location. By using Video camera, video was recorded for 15 minutes interval and the video was played again and again for the data analysis with accuracy.

3. Results and Discussion

The peak hour volume and peak hour factor was identified by the gathered quantitative data analysis. The level of service for the identified section was analyzed.

3.1 Directional traffic volume analysis

Directional traffic volume data counted at 15min interval for 1 hour. Traffic volume analysis is conducted for both directions for the section. In figure 2 it is seen that the most crossed vehicle is Auto Rickshaw in both Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction and Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station. As the highway located at the southern part of Bangladesh which is connected to Dhaka, so it is the most used intersection to shipping heavy and light goods by tuck.

Fig. 2: Traffic volume by vehicle type

Fig. 3: Traffic volume (veh/15min)

It is also seen that the common vehicle is Auto Rickshaw. People like to travel on Auto Rickshaw from one place to another in a shorter distance. And it is getting popular day by day. It was seen that the car and bus were very small in number. Motor Cycles are used in a mentionable number. Bus as Public transportation is also taking place to congest the road.

3.2 Directional Distribution

The Directional distribution is defined as the percentage of heavier volume over the total highway volume. This directional distribution is relevant only when designing or analyzing highways with two or more lanes in one direction. It can be also defined as distribution or split of the total traffic volume in two opposite directions during a particular time period. Directional distribution is used for capacity analysis, signal timing, justifying traffic control etc. The possible values of directional split vary from 50 percent to 100 percent.

Directional Distribution of Vehicle

Fig. 4: Directional Distribution of the Observed Traffic

From the Pie-Diagram it is seen that 51.41% vehicles of total traffic volume go from Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station while 48.59% vehicles go from Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction. It signifies that in a day more vehicles travel from Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station. Directional distribution also varies during morning and evening due to commuter traffic. But it is seen that the values here are very close. So, in both morning and evening there remain kind of same rush in both directions. So, it is seen that the highway exhibits fairly uniform traffic distribution. So, for now no corrective measures need not to take.

3.3 Estimation of Level of Service

Peak Hour factor (PHF) method has been applied to estimate the LOS. Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction LOS in morning is C category, in noon LOS of Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction is C and Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station is of D category. In evening peak LOS of two directions are category D. As we can see that, among these four periods lowest LOS is category C. Overall Level of Service of Faridpur-Vhanga highway was found D. Which indicates the speeds are somewhat reduced and motorists are hemmed in by other vehicles. It is typical urban peak-period highway conditions [7].

Table 3: Level of service of the given roadway by Peak Hour Factor

Time	Direction	Peak Hour Factor	LOS	Avg. LOS
8:00-9:00am	Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction	0.83	C	D
	Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station	0.89	D	
1:00-2:00pm	Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction	0.85	C	
	Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station	0.89	D	
4:00-5:00pm	Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction	0.87	D	
	Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station	0.90	D	
8:00-9:00pm	Faridpur old bus station to Vhanga junction	0.87	D	
	Vhanga junction to Faridpur old bus station	0.83	C	

The study was carried out for only 4 different hours in the morning, evening and night. So, further we can carry out a volume count survey for 24 hours. The major limitation of this volume study was the survey was conducted for 1 hour only, whereas for accurate results, the survey should be conducted for at least 3 hours. Number of enumerators was 4 where for complete and precise collection of data at least 8 persons were required. Some vehicles were using wrong way which was not included in data so this is one of the main limitations.

3.4 Traffic Safety Measurement

Throughout the careful road way geometry surveys, it has been found the average lane width is 9.5 feet. Road way geometry contains two opposite lane as well as no existence of signaling is caused negative impact such as heavy traffic congestions, fatal accidents as well. Moreover, it has also been found the average shoulder widths 2.5 feet which is very insufficient width for primary maintenance or parking for short duration.

4. Conclusion and Recommendation

4.1 Conclusion

The traffic flow behavior in heterogeneous traffic in Vhanga-Faridpur highway is observed that is absolutely complex. The findings of the research work concluded below in brief:

- Most of the vehicle in the traffic flow was Auto Rickshaw.
- The number of Auto Rickshaws and cars are more when compared to buses.
- So, if numbers of buses are increased, then the dependency on public transports increase.
- The number of personal vehicles will decrease after increasing buses.
- Hence the congestion gets reduced and free flow of traffic will be possible.
- By reducing scattered parking, proper signaling, improving level of service will reduce traffic fatality.

4.2 Recommendation

Some of the remedial measures to improve the traffic safety by providing adequate lane number i.e., changing 2-lane to 4-lane and widening the road, proper signaling and restricted scattered parking can be recommended based on the outcomes of the work.

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